

Malleability techniques applications in high-performance computing

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1. Introduction

The current static usage model of HPC systems is becoming increasingly inefficient. This is driven by the continuously growing complexity and heterogeneity of system architectures, in combination with the increased usage of coupled applications, the need for strong scaling with extreme scale parallelism, and the increasing reliance on complex and dynamic workflows. Therefore, we see a rise in research on malleable systems, middleware software and applications, which can adjust resources usage dynamically in order to extract a maximum of efficiency. By providing an intelligent global coordination of resources usage, through runtime scheduling of computation, network usage, and I/O across all components of the system architecture, malleable HPC systems can maximize the exploitation of their resources, while at the same time minimizing the makespan of applications in many, if not most, cases.

Of particular concern is the emerging class of data-intensive applications and their interaction with classic simulation workloads, driven by the growing need to process extremely large datasets. However, uncoordinated file access in combination with limited bandwidth make the I/O system a serious bottleneck. Emerging multi-tier storage hierarchies come with the potential to remove this barrier, but maximizing performance still requires careful control to avoid congestion. Malleability allows systems to dynamically adjust the computation and storage needs of applications on the one side and the global system on the other.

Such malleable systems, however, face a series of fundamental research challenges, including who initiates changes in resource availability or usage? How is it

communicated? How to compute the optimal usage? How can applications cope with dynamically changing resources? What should malleable programming models and abstractions look like? How to design resource management frameworks for malleable systems? Which resources benefit from malleability, and which (if any) should still be managed statically?

2. Contents

The special issue includes four papers, carefully selected after peer-to-peer review, presenting research works from diverse areas of HPC that are impacted by or actively pursuing malleability concepts, most of them related to the impact of system software solutions for malleability into the applications, including new programming models.

The integration of malleability in high-performance instances of the Basic Linear Algebra Subprograms (BLAS) is currently nonexistent, and, in consequence, applications relying on these computational kernels cannot benefit from this capability. [Rodriguez-Sanchez et al. \(2023\)](#) present their experience with nested parallelism in task-parallel applications using malleable BLAS on multicore processors and demonstrate that significant performance benefits can be gathered via the exploitation of malleability in a framework designed to implement portable and high-performance BLAS-like operations. For this purpose, we integrate malleability within the BLIS library and provide an experimental evaluation of the result on three different practical use cases.

In the article “Role-shifting threads: Increasing OpenMP malleability to address load imbalance at MPI and OpenMP,” [Criado et al. \(2023\)](#) show the evolution of the free

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agent threads for OpenMP to the new role-shifting threads model and their integration with the Dynamic Load Balancing (DLB) library and its integration with three real-world scientific applications. In addition, they demonstrate that the new implementation let the runtime system automatically make decisions that were made by the programmer previously.

In the article [Martin-Alvarez et al. \(2023\)](#), Martin et al. describe different methods and strategies, defining eight different alternatives to spawn processes dynamically and indicate which one should be used depending on whether a strong or weak scaling application is being used. In addition, it is described for both types of applications which strategies benefit most the application performance or the system productivity. The results show that reducing the number of spawning processes by reusing the older ones can reduce reconfiguration time compared to the classical method by up to 2.6 times for expanding and up to 36 times for shrinking.

Finally, [Cascajo et al. \(2023\)](#) introduce a novel methodology for improving the scheduling process based on the performance prediction and the detection of CPU and I/O interference between applications. This feature consists of using malleable synthetic benchmarks—called clones—that reproduce the behavior of applications executed in a cluster. These proxies can be used with two objectives: To build large and representative datasets that can be used to train the machine learning algorithms for modeling the platform workload and to evaluate in advance if two executing applications can potentially produce contention hazards related to the shared use of the system resources like CPU, cache memory, or I/O bandwidth. The proposed framework generates application clones based on generic-purpose performance information collected from monitoring. Unlike other works based on the use of micro-architectures or metrics obtained from simulators, in the approach presented in this work, the application clones generate similar behavior without extracting data from the binaries, avoiding the necessity of managing code or data from the applications.

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